

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17070709

Non-State Actors And Security Management In Anambra State, 2015-2021

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed impact of non-state actors on security management in Anambra State. The objective of the study is to; To find out non-governmental organizations has affected security management in Anambra State. To examine the impact of community based organizations on security management in Anambra State. To ascertain the impact of faith based organizations on security management in Anambra State. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The population of this study is the non-state actors in Anambra state from which three major cities will be studied. Given the number of non-state actors in Anambra State naturally fluctuates by new entry, death, the study population is therefore considered infinite. This sample size of 368 satisfied, Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that Non-governmental organizations have significant influence on security management in Anambra State. ($t=10.332$, $p, 005$); Community based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State ($t=8.543$, $p, 009$); Faith based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State. ($t=11.547$, $p, 008$). The study recommends that governments of Anambra state should, as a matter of urgency, justify their existence as a platform for the promotion of the welfare of the citizens by being alive to its responsibility of protecting the lives, liberty, and property of the people of the South East. This will make the resort to other identity platforms unnecessary. The governors in the region are also enjoined to take the lead in the negotiation for peace and to advance a counter-narrative to the people of the Anambra state on the need for unity and peaceful coexistence with other ethnic nationalities in the Nigerian federation. The study recommends that The message of unity and peaceful coexistence should also be taken to the grassroots through traditional rulers, religious leaders, and their institutions.

Keywords: Non-governmental organizations, community based organizations, Faith based organizations

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Security of lives and properties is originally a selective duty that falls in the capacity of government; cutting-across all layers of society (Ozden, & Kwabe, 2024). Threats to peace and security in the form of violent crimes and conflicts are not new in Nigeria. However, a general deterioration of internal security situation since the return to democracy in May 1999, characterized by unprecedented escalation and intensification of conflicts and criminality, is worrisome (Ezeamama and Ofozoba, 2023). Violent crimes such as armed robbery, banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling, oil theft, arms smuggling, and piracy have become increasingly perturbing. Added to these is the challenges posed by the ongoing Boko Haram

insurgency, resurgence of militancy in the Niger Delta, ethno religious crisis, communal conflicts and frequent clashes between herdsmen and their host communities (Ezeamama, Orji, and Obani, 2024).

Most times, such violent crimes and conflicts as well as associated state responses to them have proven costly in terms of human and material losses. It was recently reported that about 102,000 people were unlawfully killed by state and non-state actors between 1999 and 2016 in Nigeria (Ezeamama, 2019). The seven-year Boko Haram insurgency has claimed at least 20,000 lives and displaced more than 2.6 million people¹. Similarly, an estimated 60, 000 people have died in pastoralist-related clashes in Nigeria since 2001 (Ezeamama & Obani, 2024). The Nigerian government have leveraged security agencies and law enforcement institutions in tackling these diverse and evolving security challenges. However, government's reliance on about 377,000 policemen to cater for the security needs of over 170, 000,00 people in the country has proven grossly inadequate (Ezeora Amakoromo & Onyemaobi 2023),. Also, other factors such as the culture of corruption and politicisation have created a hollowed-out police force – strong on paper but ineffective in practice (Okenyodo, 2016).

Consequently, the military is increasingly being tasked to deal with, or complement the efforts of other security agencies in combating, violent conflicts and criminality across the country. As at February 2017, the Nigeria Army had been deployed in about 32 states of the 36 states of the Federation (Ezeamama & Orji, 2024). Yet, the military and other security agencies have had problems coping with the challenging security environment. In several states across Nigeria, groups and communities increasingly rely on informal security providers as their response to rising insecurity and declining confidence in formal state institutions, particularly the police (Kwaja, 2014). Thus, the seeming inability of formal state institutions to adequately provide security, effectively maintain law and order, and efficiently dispense justice in the society have underpinned an increase in the existence and activities of 4 non-state security actors in Nigeria (Ezeamama and Ofozoba 2023)

For close to two decades in Nigeria, the country has become a hotbed of conflicts, and it has reached a crescendo that one questions the place and the reactions of the Nigerian state in this regards, when it is well indicated that it has the legitimate right to the use of violence. The challenges of life threatening the survival of the country have become complex to the extent that the country now has to run to non-state actors (the Para-police) that are less- armed and poor training for complementary assistance and survival. It is important to note that NSAs in general, can be on either side of the security spectrum (Iwuagwu, Etta, & Agabi, 2022). In other words, they can either be the cause of insecurity or the solution to insecurity. Sometimes too, as a result of inadequate training, they apply excessive force to maintain order, which is an aberration to the norm. Hence, it is from this standpoint that we will be discussing non-violent NSAs who serve to bring about solutions to insecurity. Therefore, examining the place of these non-state actors in assisting the Federal Police and other national security agencies in combating insecurity in Nigeria prompted this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Defence Realism

Defence Realism, formulated by Kenneth Waltz explains the inevitability of NSAs in the security sector. Defence Realism is a structural theory of international relations that theorizes that the power struggle in the international system allows for states to adapt, create and moderate policies that allow them to attain maximum internal security (Dougherty& Pfaltzgraff, Jr, 1990).It also supports the traditional realist assumptions that survival is the principal goal of every state actor and that given the anarchical nature of the international system, states require to constantly ensure that they have sufficient power to defend themselves and advance interests required for survival. This theory has been used to justify the acquisition of nuclear weapons by powerful states in the international system.

The theory asserts that the creation of defensive mechanisms only arises from the existence of an offensive realism which is imminent in the international system. In other words, Waltz proposed that states conform and react to the threats they face internally and externally which leads them to operate on

contingency plans and NSAs are a form of contingency to deal with the alarming conflict. This aligns with traditional thinking of realists who assume states as primary actors and would do anything (including participating in joint security and the creation of local groups) to protect their territories and ensure state survival as the international system is presumed anarchical in nature. Defence Realism is thus, adopted as tool for the analysis of the changing role of non-violent NSAs in securing Nigeria.

2.2 Empirical Review

Lord-Mallam, (2024) scrutinized non-violent NSAs' functions and obligations in Nigeria's security sector. The paper, through content analysis, argues that although the abuse of power is sometimes carried out by these NSAs, most times, if properly trained and guided, are well organised and work to support state apparatus. It then concludes that, Nigeria's NSAs, like those of other states, emerge as an alternative to state security's failure to provide adequate security for the lives and properties of its citizens. The paper concludes by urging the Nigerian state to commit to encouraging entities with solutions to insecurity to come up with them. The paper makes a case for collaborative policing, jointly managed by the state and the NSAs. It suggests that organized means of engaging non-violent NSAs through delegating specific obligations to them would help curb insecurity in Nigeria.

Udochukwu, et al. (2024) focused on the pragmatic analysis of waning capacity of the police and Armed Forces in curtailing the bludgeoning activities of armed non-state actors. Data were largely drawn for secondary sources of security reports. The paper affirmed that the violent activities of armed non-state actors accounts mostly for the deaths of Nigerians who died through killings. The paper also affirmed that the centralized architecture and organization of the Nigerian security system has made the police and the armed forces less effective. The paper concluded that national security will not thrive as long as violent non-state actors have free reign. The paper suggested the adoption and integration of community policing as part of the country's security architecture through constitutional provisions.

Azubiike., Ojo & Igboke (2023) examined the role of non-state actors in international terrorism with special emphasis on ISIS and Boko Haram as cases under review. The paper examined the complex and evolving roles of non-state actors, specifically ISIS and Boko Haram, in international conflicts. It delves into issues surrounding recruitment, radicalization, transnational impact, and responses by states and international community. By investigating these aspects, the study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges posed by these groups and inform more effective counterterrorism strategies and policies. The research questions that guided this study are, how do non-state actors contribute to local and international conflict, and what are the implications for global security? The research objective was to analyze the strategies employed by these two groups to achieve their objectives and to evaluate the effectiveness of the measures adopted by the international community to combat their activities. The theoretical framework adopted in this study is the Terrorism and Insurgency theory seeks to explain and understand the use of violence and intimidation by non-state actors to achieve political, ideological or social objectives, with its use of armed struggle against government or occupying force, often involving guerrilla warfare and popular support, with the aim of achieving political change, and sometime independence. The findings of this study revealed that non-state actors like ISIS and Boko Haram pose a significant threat to global security, as they are able to carry out attacks on a global scale and destabilize entire regions.

Mkpae, (2024) examined the Role of Non-state Actors in Shaping International Security. Insecurity posed a grave threat to lives, properties and the social displacement of people. Several lives have been lost as a result of the activities deadly non-state actors. The realist theory was deployed as the theoretical framework of the study. Secondary source of data was adopted for the study; it involves the collection of data from textbooks, journals and seminar papers amongst others. The study observed that there is a strong links among dead non-state actors in the international system such as ISIL, Alqaeda, and Al-shabaab among others. This has enabled them to share arms, ammunitions and information. The study recommends that national governments need to demonstrate commitments not only in policy formulation, endorsement of agreements and codification, but also practical effort at implementation need be put in

place, and to also, meet their primary responsibility to provide social and economic security and development for their citizens.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

The research design adopted in this study will be the survey design because it ensures that the data collected is reliable, valid, and actionable. This allows for informed decision-making based on the survey results.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study is the non-state actors in Anambra state from which three major cities will be studied. Given the number of non-state actors in Anambra State naturally fluctuates by new entry, death, the study population is therefore considered infinite.

3.3 Determination of the Sample Size

Since the population is infinite, the sample size of the study was determined with the aid of Cochran's non-parametric sample size determination formula. A pilot survey on 100 respondents (spouses/couples) from within the study area was conducted in order to test the authenticity of the research instrument. Q and p values obtained from their responses were recorded as, 40 and 60 respectively and calculated on Cochran's formula for sample size determination as shown below

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

e²

where

n = Sample size

z = The value of Z-score associated with the selected degree of confidence limit
(95%) i.e. = constant = 1.96

p = probability of positive response 40/100 = 0.4

q = probability of negative response 60/100 = 0.6

e = tolerable error or error margin = 5% = 0.05

Substituting therefore,

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.4 \times 0.6}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.4 \times 0.6}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.921984}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 368.4$$

This sample size of 368 satisfied. Malhotra and Birks (2000) stand that 300 to 530 respondents are considered acceptable sample size that is adequate for quantitative consumer survey, where the population

is not known. The sample size was equally distributed among the major cities and between the anambra habitant who age goes between 18-70 years. The biggest city was allocated the balance of two members. The table below shows the details.

S/n	City	Sample size	Sample size
1	Nnewi	124	62
2	Awka	122	61
3	Onitsha	122	61
		368	368

3.4 Sampling Technique

The study will adopt convenience sampling. Only respondents who are willing and are ready to participate in the study will be investigated.

3.5: Sources of Data

The primary data will be used in this study. The questionnaire will be used to obtain the data

3.6 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

Statistics, including frequency count tables and percentages were put to use in the analysis of personal characteristics and data analysis, while research hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis. The research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis were carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), (Version 23).

PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents through the administered questionnaire. Three hundred and ninety-nine (399) were administered amongst the choice of political candidate in Imo State. However; Three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved, while fifty-two (52), were not mutilated, while some were lost on the process of collection. Therefore, the analysis and interpretation of data were based only on the returned questionnaire.

Table 4.1: Respondents' Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	172	49.6
Female	175	50.4
Total	347	100%
Marital status		
Single	70	20.2
Married	234	67.4
widowed/divorced/separated	43	12.4
Total	347	100
Educational Qualification		
No formal studies	36	10.4
Primary	27	7.8
Post-primary	53	15.3
Tertiary	231	66.6
Total	347	100

Age category		
18-29	179	51.6
30-40	74	21.3
41-50	84	24.2
51-60		
61-above	10	2.9
Total	347	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The above table reveals that the one hundred and seventy-two (172) of the respondents which represents 49.4 percent were male respondents, while one hundred and seventy-five (175) respondents which represent 50.4% were female respondents. By implication, female respondents were more than male respondents by 3 respondents in our selected population sample for this study.

Still In the table 4.1 above, out of the three hundred and forty-seven (347) respondents, two hundred and thirty-four (234) of the respondents were married, while seventy (70) respondents which represent 20.2 percent are single. However, the remaining 43 respondent, which is 12.4 percent fall under widowed/divorced/separated. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents are married as at the time of this study.

The table 4.1 also indicates that thirty-six (36) respondents representing 10.4% percent have no formal education, while 7.8% percent of the respondents which represents twenty-seven (27) had primary school certification. However fifty-three (53) respondents which represent 15.3 had post-primary school education. Lastly, two hundred and thirty-one (231) which represent 66.6 percent had tertiary school education. It is clear that educated respondents constitutes the greatest percentage.

Table 4.1 above depicted the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 5.1% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 34 years, while 21.3% respondents are within the age bracket of 35-49 years. On the same note, 24.2% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 60-69 years. On the same note, 2.9% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 70 years and above. This results shows that the respondents are mostly youths

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

The need to examine the relationship between the collected data and the stated hypothesis has called for this section. This result will be compared with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in this research work holds or not.

Hypotheses One

Ho₁: Non-governmental organizations have no significant influence on security management in Anambra State.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3242.5981	3	1794.190	10.332	.015
Within Groups	6734.279	344	378.389		
Total	77436.800	347			

Sources: SPSS Output, 2025

The test table reveal that wide significance value (F. sig<.05) indicate group differences. Since the F-value of 10.332 which has a significance of .015 is less than .05 (i.e .001<.05), there exist no group difference among the variables. Non-governmental organizations have significant influence on security management in Anambra State

Hypotheses Two

Ho₂: Community based organizations has no significant influence on security management in Anambra State.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4838.324	2	2419.162	8.543	.009
Within Groups	6598.476	345	388.146		
Total	11436.800	347			

Sources: SPSS Output, 2025

We discover that in the F-statistics column the value for Types of identity theft is 8.543, while its probability is 0.009 since its probability is less than 0.05% desired level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis, which states that Community based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State

Hypotheses Three

Ho₃: Faith based organizations has no significant influence on security management in Anambra State

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2839.200	1	1419.600	11.547	.008
Within Groups	8597.600	346	505.741		
Total	11436.800	347			

Sources: SPSS Output, 2025

From the regression result, we discover that in the F-statistics column the value for identity Mentoring is 11.547, while its probability is 0.88 since its probability is greater than 0.05% desired level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternative hypothesis, which states that Faith based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of the Findings

The basic objective of this study is to assess the impact of non-state actors on security management in Anambra State. To empirically and statically establish the nature of the relationship in Nigeria three hundred and ninety-four (347) respondents were randomly selected three hundred and sixty-eight (368) questionnaires were returned and analysis of the data were based on this number. From the analysis of the data especially, and the testing of hypothesis it was realized that:

- i. Non-governmental organizations have significant influence on security management in Anambra State. (t=10.332, p, 005)
- ii. Community based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State (t=8.543, p, 009)
- iii. Faith based organizations has significant influence on security management in Anambra State. (t=11.547, p, 008)

5.2 CONCLUSION

Non-state actors significantly impact security management in Nigeria, both positively and negatively. They include vigilante groups, ethnic militias, and terrorist organizations, each with varying degrees of influence. While some non-state actors like vigilantes can provide local security, others, such as terrorist

groups, exacerbate insecurity. The presence and activities of these actors challenge the state's monopoly on the use of force and complicate efforts to maintain peace and order. Vigilante groups and community-based security initiatives often fill the gap where formal security agencies are perceived as inadequate, providing a sense of security to local communities. Non-state actors, especially those operating within communities, may have better intelligence on local security threats than formal agencies, aiding in crime prevention. In some instances, non-state actors have played a role in mediating local conflicts, helping to de-escalate tensions and prevent violence

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the finding the following recommendation are made

- i. The study recommends that governments of Anambra state should, as a matter of urgency, justify their existence as a platform for the promotion of the welfare of the citizens by being alive to its responsibility of protecting the lives, liberty, and property of the people of the South East. This will make the resort to other identity platforms unnecessary.
- ii. The governors in the region are also enjoined to take the lead in the negotiation for peace and to advance a counter-narrative to the people of the Anambra state on the need for unity and peaceful coexistence with other ethnic nationalities in the Nigerian federation.
- iii. The study recommends that The message of unity and peaceful coexistence should also be taken to the grassroots through traditional rulers, religious leaders, and their institutions.

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